

SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF GLOBAL PROBLEMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article contains some thoughts about global problems and their impact on our social life and to what extent their social importance is evaluated in Uzbekistan.

Key words: global, hunger, poverty, etymology, education, humanity, globalization, resonance effect, society.

What are global problems? The concept of "contemporary global problems" became widespread in the late 1960s and early 1970s, and since then it has taken a firm place in scientific and political discourse (lexicon) and public consciousness. In most cases, it is used as a term applied to global events and events. Such a situation can be encountered when events of national and universal importance are equated, for example, referring to the social problems of a particular country and calling them "global".

Etymologically, the term "global", like the term "globalization", is related to the globe. It is for this reason that it is customary to name the problems that affect the interests of all humanity, as well as the problems that belong to each person in different parts of the world, that is, they acquire a universal character, as "global". They significantly affect the development of some countries and regions as an important objective factor of world economic and social development. Solving them requires the joint efforts of most countries and organizations at the international level. At the same time, failure to solve global problems can have disastrous consequences for the future of all mankind.

The progress of human society has never been easy and unobstructed anywhere. At all times and in all times, certain problems have been facing the society. These are, on the one hand, earthquakes, floods, droughts, various epidemic diseases associated with changes in solar radiation, which appear as a result of natural disasters, and on the other hand, they are caused by human activity. are anthropogenic problems related to socio-economic, political and cultural life.

Analysis of global processes shows that the following are the acute and urgent global problems for humanity at the moment:

- a) Ensuring peace on earth and preventing wars of mass destruction (problem of war and peace);
- b) effective environmental protection (ecological problem);
- d) achieving the ratio of production development with the increase in population (demographic problem);
- e) reliable provision of necessary food and energy resources to the population of the earth;
- f) elimination of the sharp difference between highly developed and lagging countries in order to end hunger, poverty and backwardness;
- g) elimination of dangerous diseases;

h) ensuring the purity of human spiritual and moral environment (problem of ethics) and others.

Each of these problems has been scientifically analyzed from a social, political, economic, and legal point of view

The main aspects of globalization are the significant changes in the world market, the world economy manifesting its own characteristics and becoming stronger and more important than national economies. The following are the main aspects of globalization.

a) the emergence of the "resonance effect", in which economic booms or crises pass from one country to other countries and regions that are closely related to it;

b) creation of world markets of various goods and services;

the specified goods and services, they determine the policy of national producers of these goods and services in many ways.

Among the various approaches to the classification of global problems today, according to the most widely recognized classification, all global problems are divided into three large groups depending on the level of tension and importance of their solution, as well as the existence of causal connections between them in real life .

The first group is the problems characterized by the greatest generality and level of importance. They arise from relations between different countries. That is why they are called intersocial global problems. It is here to eliminate war from the life of society and ensure a just world; two very important problems such as the establishment of a new international economic order are distinguished.

The second group are problems arising from the interaction of society and nature, such as providing people with energy, fuel, fresh water, raw materials, etc. This group includes environmental problems, as well as the exploitation of the World Ocean and outer space.

The third group The problems related to the "Man - society" system are demographic problems, health care, education, the threat of international terrorism, spiritual issues, and so on.

The inclusion of this or that problem in a certain group is conditional to a certain extent and depends on important factors and the basis of their separation. Therefore, any classification should be considered not as a short-term solution to the problem, but as one of the methods of restructuring a complex system that helps to better understand the nature of the global problem interaction.

Bekzod Zokirov, a doctoral student at the University of Tokyo, Japan, expresses his opinion in this regard .

The expert said that the main task of the republic **is to create an institutional environment that strengthens the cooperation of** the three parties important for technological development: the state-industry-academy (scientific research centers).

" Universities and their research centers , which are the main part of the triangle , are not only sources of inventions that support businesses in various industries, but also serve as incubators for startups based on various innovative ideas. It is not for nothing that startups are formed in the university area in almost all developed countries in the USA, Europe and Asia. For this, it is necessary to have a free scientific environment in the universities , to form a strong patent system so that the scientific ideas and works of professors and students do not remain on paper, but are used in practice," says Bekzod Zakirov.

At the same time, he noted that the successful integration of Uzbekistan into the hyperglobal economy is based on the following issues.

First of all, the integration of the state into the global economy and achieving superiority in it, first of all, begins with the economy that is formed in the country, its form, clear direction and internal stability. That is, the parameters of integration into the global economy can be a springboard for growth only for economies that are ready for development, and integration cannot stimulate economic growth for an economy whose foundation is built on wrong principles. The success of Uzbekistan in the global economy is related to the economic model it is building. The future of Uzbekistan's economy depends on whether it remains an exporter of raw materials subject to constant changes, or whether it produces high-value products and joins the global supply chain, which is the lifeblood of international trade.

Second, the success of the state in the global economy is related to its institutional preparation, which absorbs frequent global crises and shocks and reduces the impact on the domestic economy. This is because international trade and free movement of capital, which are the main components of hyper-globalization, unfortunately create losers as well as winners within the country. This is seen in the impoverishment due to job losses due to free trade competition. As a developing country facing globalism, Uzbekistan should be ready to eliminate socio-economic problems arising from trade liberalization and to protect the losers through free trade. Also, the government should follow the example of the unprepared and inexperienced liberalization of financial markets, which has cost many countries, and be extremely careful about the movement of unregulated capital flows.

In the modern world, industrialized countries are trying to control the flow of information influence to developing countries. The Western way of life promotes a consumerist psychology that is deeply embedded in people's minds. In the spiritual sphere, in the sphere of culture, globalization remains one of the most important in the evolutionary development of the world. It is necessary to note the very important positive factors related to wide-scale cultural contacts, communication, expansion of opportunities to gain positive experience, enrichment of national cultures and expansion of their opportunities to make a significant contribution to the development of the common culture of humanity. But here it is necessary to take measures to preserve and protect the uniqueness of traditional national cultures and their creative development as a result of contact with other cultures. It should be remembered that the two opposite world trends, such as globalization and localization, with all their interdependence, often lead to the intensification of conflicts, especially on a national-religious basis. Young people are often defined as a separate social segment of society, which differs from other strata of society by age. This social group can be seen as the most active means of growth and development of global media culture, because it is young people who are the largest informational and technologically advanced layer of modern society. It should be remembered that the global multinational corporations that carry out commercial activities in the mass media purposefully choose the youth environment as the main audience, because at the moment this layer of society is the most preferred in the commercial and consumer plan. Global youth culture relies heavily on the concept of the modern culture industry, which includes the process of promoting the global integration of society through industrialized, popular culture and norms of behavior. At the same time, young people are becoming a part of this global cultural system, because they are directly involved and are active participants in new innovations in the field of media technologies. This allows global

mass media companies to attract young people to their channels as representatives of the "mass culture" of developed capitalist countries, replacing national and traditional cultures with universal standard values that indirectly support the geopolitical goals of countries such as the United States and the West. will give.

The important role of the Internet in the process of globalization of youth culture cannot be denied. The members of the Internet community create a new culture because the communication between their participants can be considered as a social voice within the Internet space. Due to the specificity of these interactions, cultural and spiritual changes occur. Today, one of the most important tasks facing modern society is the preservation of cultural heritage and the modernization of social consciousness, especially is to seek and establish a mutually beneficial consensus among young people. Globalization in the field of culture leads to the acceleration of the main processes of the formation of a wide spectrum of modern culture - "consumer culture" is the increase of values and the lack of evaluation decisions, all familiar things in new conditions is characterized by overwriting with.

In conclusion, we understand that the unification of cultures is becoming a global problem, serious threats, many traditions, rituals that gave diversity to humanity in the past, are gradually disappearing as the main part of society adopts new standard forms of life. Given globalization, it is necessary to develop a spiritual and cultural immunity to our culture and the ideal mentality of mass Western culture. It is necessary to promote national ideology, ideas of national identity, unique culture in Internet space and mass media. In order to achieve complete development, raise the level of spirituality and form immunity against foreign ideology, it is necessary to promote the ideas of national independence in the family, school, neighborhood and higher education institutions. In addition, these issues should be covered in the media by involving scholars, writers, lawyers and politicians at all levels of society.

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